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*Corresponding

Author:- Rakesh
Sharma

Surgery NMR Lab,
Massachusetts General
Hospital, Boston MA;
SMMH Government
Medical College,
Saharanpur, UP India

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Renal and Adrenal cancer: Clinical Course, Nanomedicine, Relapse and Optimal Management of Adrenal Metastases using Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality methods

Rakesh Sharma

*Surgery NMR Lab, Massachusetts General Hospital,
Boston MA; SMMH Government Medical College,
Saharanpur, UP India*

ABSTRACT

Advanced renal cancer poses a life threat. Most likely it represents a renal cell carcinoma, metastasis and adrenal gland metastasis with direct clinical course. The renal metastases may pose resistance to immunotherapy with only option of local therapy and surgery left. Molecular profiling, next-generation sequencing, tumor mutation burden testing of PBRM1, SETD2 and VHL mutations, genomic BAP1, PD-L1 profiling and apoptosis biomarkers characterize the renal and adrenal metastases; 2. Artificial intelligence algorithms for better tumor classification and monitoring treatment response after chemotherapy, radiation and surgery interventions. New therapeutic genomic agents and nanochemoprevention are more effective theranostic options. In more advanced therapeutic resistant lesions, ablation therapy is choice after immunotherapy of both renal and adrenal metastases either relapse or remained residual disease. Management with local therapy, interleukin-2 therapy in relapsed lesions, immune-check point inhibitor therapy and antivascular therapy may induce durable remissions. Artificial intelligence, virtual reality and robotic methods are emerging.

Keywords:-*Renal and adrenal cancer, next-generation sequencing, apoptosis, Artificial intelligence, nanochemoprevention, immunotherapy, theranosis, renal cancer relapse patterns, optimal management, renal cancer clinical trials*

INTRODUCTION

Renal and adrenal cancer is an advanced disease. The chapter describes an account on clinical course, nanomedicine, clinical trials on relapse and optimal management of renal cell carcinoma and adrenal metastases, use of artificial intelligence and virtual reality methods.

Normal Physiochemical Role of Kidneys and adrenal glands

Kidneys are two bean-shaped organs located on both right and left sides of spine below rib cage. Adrenal glands are small, triangular glands located on top of kidneys on both sides. Adrenal glands produce hormones that instruct to every organ and tissues in the body.

Fig.1:- Histology of normal kidney (ontop) and comparison of renal carcinoma vs normal (on bottom).

Abnormal Physiochemical Changes Towards Renal and Adrenal Cancers

Kidneys develop renal cortical tumors or cancer starts in either the blood-filtering glomerulus called renal cortical tumor or renal pelvis called urothelial bladder cancer.

Over 51000 males and females were diagnosed each year in last 5 years. Males were affected twice as often as females. However, rarely children also develop renal cancer. Most common is adult kidney cancer or renal cell carcinoma.

Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) is a heterologous disease as set of 40 subtypes with survival spanning from few months to several years. These subtypes include 70% clear cell RCC, 15% papillary and 5% chromophobe RCC, and others. Use of nanomedicines is emerging in renal cancer clinical management and prevention of metastasis recurrence risk evaluation.

International Metastatic Disease Consortium (IMDC) defined recurrence risk profile using clinical factors such as nephrectomy, anemia, performance status, calcium, lactate dehydrogenase levels, platelet count, and neutrophil count [1]. The IMDC criteria defines prognosis into: no risk (0 factors), intermediate risk (1–2 risk factors), and high risk (3 or more factors) categories. Presently, WHO/ISUP laid tumor grading by TNM staging system in classes of sarcoma, microvascular invasion, tumor necrosis, invasion of collecting system. In present time, tumor biopsy next-generation sequencing techniques have explored

several theranostic gene variations, RNA expressions, alternative RNA splicing events and gene fusion data as bioinformatics outcome. The RCC amounts 85% of total cases. Renal cell carcinoma is classified broadly into four types based on tumor behavior.

1. Renal clear cell carcinoma: About 75-80% renal cell carcinoma is associated with loss of some part of chromosome-3 gene known as loss of von Hippel-Lindau gene.
2. Papillary cancer: About 10-15% renal cell carcinoma tumors are developed in multiple parts of kidney. They may be found in both kidneys at diagnosis.
3. Chromophobe carcinoma: About 5-10% renal cell carcinoma show good outcome with low risk of progression or death in comparison to clear cell carcinoma.
4. Oncocytoma: About 3-7% renal cell carcinoma remain silent over years and rarely become invasive or spread out.

Fig. 2:- (On top left) A tumor RCC classification TCGA system with immunofluorescence staining system (on right). Tumor staging in I,II,III,IV grades of RCC shows renal cell features (at bottom). Reproduced with permission from reference [5].

Other very rare form of kidney cancer is collecting duct tumors in young patients.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON RCC PATIENTS

Databases of PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane Library and Web of Science were searched on advanced RCC presents with adrenal metastases from RCC as a solitary site or as dominant areas of relapse/residual disease [1]. These patients were evaluated for demographics, liquid biopsy molecular profiles or fingerprints, sites of metastases, IMDC prognostic risk characteristics, therapy, response rates, and progression free and overall survival assessed by nanoparticle assisted molecular profiling data of renal cancer specific patterns distinct from normal renal adrenal cells with/without burden of adrenal metastases [2]. Following section describes recent diagnostic methods of renal cancer.

DIAGNOSIS OF RENAL CANCER

1. presence of molecular profile in cancer or precancer cells,

2. active infection by urine culture,
3. cyst or tumor 3D image by Computed, ultrasound and renal blood vessels by Magnetic Resonance Imaging,
4. needle biopsy histology to identify cancer cells and type.

Serum and urine fluids are choice to identify chemical compounds by liquid chromatography combined with mass spectrometry LC-MS [3][4], surface assisted Laser desorption/ionization (SALDI) MS. Increased serum glucose, lactate, leucine, myo-inositol, 1-methylhistidine indicated RCC at different stages [2].

RCC LIQUID BIOPSIES

Gene regulating non-coding MicroRNA15a was detected in the body fluids of RCC by qRT-PCR method [6]. RCC tumor grade specific specific extracellular vesicles (EV) were visualized by TEM nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) of exosomes rich in CA9, CD70, CD147 cancer biomarkers [7]. Recently, circulating tumor cells (CTC) in blood on microfluidic AgSiO₂ chip were

reported by surface-enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) [8].

INTACT RCC TUMOR TISSUE TESTS FOR MOLECULAR PROFILING

Mainly molecular profiling immunohistochemistry and immunofluorescence tests confirm the differentiation/proliferation of RCC tumors. European Association of Urology guideline recommends molecular profiling genomic tests as earlier predictors for nephrectomy over nephron-sparing surgery option.

In ccRCC vs papillary-type RCC prognosis, selected common genes of ATG13, HBG1, HUS1B check-point proteins were reported as prognostic prediction features in earlier studies [9],[20]. Other common genes CACNA1D, CASP9, CENPBD1, CTSG, EIF5B, EYA1, FABP7, FGFR3, GPR68, LINC01512, NFE2L3, RXRA, SLC22A16, SMIM3, SMLR1, TBX18, TMEM244, TNFSF4, TOB1 and UFSP2 also showed distinct cancer specific expressions [10]. Specific gene action with physiological functions in RCC and influence on prognosis is shown in Table 1.

Table 1:-Action of gene expression and influence on physiological functions in RCC.

Checkpoint protein	Prognostic Gene Action on damaged DNA	DNA Repair mechanism	Physiological function and prognosis in RCC
HUS1B	Binds to Rad9,Rad1	Triggers cell cycle checkpoint signaling	Papillary RCC with Metastases
CACNA1D	Binds to voltage dependent L-type α 1D Ca ⁺ channels	Low expressed gene	Altered cell cycle in renal cancer cells in RCC
CASPase-9	Binds to rs12124078 SNP	Enhanced apoptosis	Enhanced programmed death of renal cell carcinoma ccRCC
Cathepsin-G	Inhibition	Enhanced apoptosis	Enhanced programmed death of renal cell carcinoma(Caki cells)
Fatty Acid Bound Protein 7	Binds to fatty acids	Overexpressed gene in ccRCC	Poor survival in advanced cancer with distant metastasis
Fibroblast Growth Factor Receptor-3	Mutated in metastasis	Downregulate in RCC	Regulate proliferation,Apoptosis and differentiation towards fibrosis and metastases
Nucleated Factor Erythroid 2-Factor 3	Binds to erythroid cells	Overexpressed gene in ccRCC	Poor survival in ccRCC

WHAT REMAINS TO EXPLORE OTHER PREDICTORS?

Other RCC specific genes F2RL1, FABP7, GPX3, HOXC10, ITGA2, LGALS2, LGALS1, MPZL2, NNMT, RGS1, S100A4, SLPI, SPINT2, TNFAIP6, UFSP2, VCAM1 and VEGF were reported as potential predictive markers in future [10].

Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), Total Mutation Burden (TMB) and PD-L1 Staining

NCG is performed on genomic DNA extracted from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tumor samples using NextSeq platform available with Illumina Inc. CA. After that, SureSelect XT assay available from Agilent Technologies, CA, was used to enrich gene target variants on 592-gene NGS panel with >99% confidence. Above target variant frequencies are measured based on allele frequency and baited capture pull-down coverage with an average sequencing depth of over 500X and an analytic sensitivity of 5% variant frequency [11].

Total mutation Burden (TMB) is calculated based on non-synonymous number of mutations identified by NGS and excluding any single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) in dbSNP or 1000 Genome Project database (phase 3). The TMB is reported as mutations per megabase sequenced with threshold of 10 or more mutations/megabase [12].

PD-L1 immunohistochemistry analysis is performed on FFPE tumor samples using immunohistochemical staining by primary antibody SP142 against PD-L1 (Spring Bioscience, Pleasanton, CA). Positive staining of both antibodies on >1% tumor cells indicates RCC positive [13].

In vivo RCC Tissue Detection by Nanotechnology

Nonmalignant tumor nature is confirmed by AgNPET/AuNPET-SELDI MS visible

octadecanamide ion for minimal risk of positive margins to suggest nephron-sparing surgery [14][15]. Recently, a capture antibody –biomimetic cell-dendrimer platform was reported to detect precise RCC-CTCs in RCC patients [16]. Other clinical developments are nanobubble-assisted RCC tumor specific anti-G250 imaging by ultrasound [17] and RCC specific lymphotropic G250-mAb-SPIO [18], AS1411-mn-MoS₂ quantum dot [19], Fe₂O₃-mSiO₂/PDDA/BSA-Gd₂O₃ assisted MRI imaging of different RCC tumor stages [20]. However, very slow progress is reported on PET real-time images of RCC cancer cells. Overall, above imaging methods characterize the cancer cells, tumor tissue and renal mass towards RCC cancer precision medicine.

Nanochemoprevention of RCC cancer

Nanochemoprevention of renal cell carcinoma (RCC) is achieved by targeted delivery of anticancer chemopreventive drugs such as hydrophobic 2'-hydroxyflavonone phytochemicals, anticancer chemopreventive novel small molecule inhibitors. The mechanism behind the nanochemoprevention is modification of miRNA regulation in renal cancer cells [21].

A review on RCC nanochemoprevention using Pubmed, Google Scholar and Science Direct resources on renal cell carcinoma, chemoprevention, nanochemoprevention, nanotechnology, phytochemicals, nanoparticles, and targeted drug delivery showed RCC related biological processes or nanoparticles – cancer cell component interactions at nanoscale [22][23]. These interactions were speculated to develop therapeutic systems approved for clinical use. [24].

Cancer nanotechnology offers hybrid design of nanocontrast agents in RCC cancer diagnosis, chemoprevention and treatment [25][26]. Nanoparticles loaded

with drugs or imaging agents can be targeted to tumors directly. Due to the small size of these nanoparticles, they have the ability to infiltrate tumors deeply with

a high degree of specificity [27]. A nanotechnology mediated therapy option for RCC is illustrated in Figure 3 with an account in Table 2.

Table 2:-Applications of nanoparticles in diagnosis of renal cell carcinoma staging by molecular profiles, imaging.

Diagnosis	Diagnostic agent	Advantages in RCC
Laboratory examination	1. Gold nanoparticles-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry 2. High-resolution MRS and silver-109 nanoparticle enhanced steel target laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry	1. Distinct MS patterns of RCC tumor grades and stages 2. Real-time monitoring of clinical prognosis and diagnosis of RCC
Molecular Profiling	1. Gold nanoparticle enhanced target 2. Silver nanoparticle enhanced target 3. Magnetic nanoparticle with immobilized trypsin 4. Biotin-streptavidin binding and fluorescence active magnetic nanocarriers	1. Differentiate between normal and cancerous RCC renal tissue 2. Distinguish healthy and RCC cancer tissue 3. Differentially cluster renal oncocytoma and chromophobe RCC 4. Detectable low levels of miRNA15a through miRNA capturing nanocarriers in RCC
Imaging	1. Lymphotropic nanoparticle-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging 2. ^{99m} Tc-nanocolloid	1. Distinguish benign from RCC malignant lymph node involvement 2. Sentinel node mapping of RCC renal tumors

Cancer chemoprevention in most common RCC disease is achieved by dietary or phytochemicals and synthetic compounds to prevent, reverse or delay carcinogenesis process [28]. Natural phytochemicals show limited action in nanoprevention with challenges of low bioavailability and biodistribution in clinical trials. The nanotechnology application is expanding for cancer nanoprevention in cancer prevention and treatment.

OPTIMAL TREATMENT OF RENAL CANCER

Local Therapy

Systemic chemotherapy (sorafenib, tyrosine kinase inhibitor, sunitinib, doxorubicin, decitabine, plitidepsin, chlorogenic acid, lupeol, vinorelbine, silibinin, lonidamine, VEGFR, AIM2 gene, PH1/pHGFK1, siRNA-143, siVEGF, siLim1) are used to kill renal cancer cells along with radiation therapy using high powered X-Ray and proton energy beams [29].

However, chemo-drugs show drug resistance most of the times due to cytotoxicity, immune response, chronic inflammation.

Fig.3:- Chemotherapeutic action of different anticancer nanodrugs (nanocarrier containing chemodrugs) is shown on renal cell carcinoma tumor cells with different targets.

Nanomedicine

In present time, nanochemo-medicines as smart nanocarriers to release drugs rapidly at target sites serve as theranostic double purpose (tracking tumor tissue changes and monitoring the nanodrug performance route or tumor response) nanorobots for image-guided surgery, targeted therapy, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, gene therapy, immunotherapy and synergetic therapy. Big efforts were devoted to develop nanomedicines for image-guided surgery (peptide nanofibers) curcuma wenyujin; targeted drugs (PLGA-DPPC liposomes); chemotherapy (liposomes, hypoxia nanoplateforms, PEG-EGCG micelle); chemotherapy (liposomes, oxygen nanocarrier); radiotherapy (black phosphorus quantum dots); native chmodrugs (nanopolymers, chitosan colloids, polycaprolactones, gelatin nanofibers, gold nanoparticles, selenium nanoparticles, magnetic nanopolymers); photothermal therapy (TiO₂-P nanorods, tLyP-1/PR-619/Fe₃O₄-PCM nanoparticles, silica nanoparticles, gold nanorods); gene therapy (polyethyleneimine, neutral lipid envelope, H1/pAIM2 nanoparticles, lipid

nanoparticles, multifunctional envelope type device (MEND), nanogel, polydiacetyenic nanofibers, glycogen polycationic derivatives, polyion complex); tumor vaccines (H1-nanoparticles, chitosan nanoparticles) as shown in Figure 3 [29]. Only few of them were reported in clinical trials using ^{99m}Tc-nanocolloid [30], siRNA targeting VEGF-kinesin spindle protein LNP lipid nanoparticles [31].

Immune Checkpoint Therapies (ICI)

The ICI have potential for durable remission in kidney cancer therapeutics with less toxicity [32]. Many multiple RCC cases, however, evidenced residual adrenal metastases or sites of relapse after immune-ICI based regimens indicating ICI resistance. RCC patients with adrenal metastases showed features of clinical course, presentation, and response to ICI therapy for specific clinical management of adrenal metastases cases within RCC. If all above chemotherapy and radiation therapy are insufficient, cryoablation and local local surgery options are used to remove affected part by nephrectomy

procedure along with other parts of affected organs.

CLINICAL GUIDELINE ON RELAPSE AND RCC DISEASE MANAGEMENT

Most authentic clinical guideline on RCC management was defined as Kidney Cancer Research Network of Canada

2019(KCRNC) with introduction of immunotherapy combined with vascular endothelial growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitor sunitinib(VEGF-TKI) phase 3 trial [33]. The guideline defines management of two categories: 1. locally advanced kidney cancer, and 2. Second-line for advanced metastasis kidney cancer.

Table 3:-A most recent clinical guideline (KCRNC 2019) suggests combined chemotherapeutic options for untreated and second-line treatment of RCC for optimal management .

Setting	Patients	Preferred	Options
Untreated Second-line and beyond	Favorable-risk (IMDC)	Pembrolizumab+Axitinib Nivolumab+Cabozantinib Lenvatinib+Pembrolizumab	Sunitinib Pazopanib Axitinib+Avelumab Active surveillance
	Intermediate-/poor-risk (IMDC)	Ipilimumab+Nivolumab Pembrolizumab+Axitinib Nivolumab+Cabozantinib Lenvatinib+Pembrolizumab	Sunitinib Pazopanib Cabozantinib Axitinib+Avelumab Active surveillance
	Prior VEGF inhibitor	Nivolumab Cabozantinib	Lenvatinib+Everolimus Axitinib Everolimus
	Prior immune checkpoint inhibitor		Axitinib Cabozantinib Lenvatinib+Everolimus Pazopanib Sunitinib
	Prior VEGF and immune checkpoint inhibitor		Axitinib Cabozantinib Lenvatinib+Everolimus Pazopanib Sunitinib

‘Preferred’ options improve overall survival. ‘Options’ show progression-free survival advantage.

Management of locally advanced kidney cancer

- Neoadjuvant therapy by VEGFR-TKI and immune check-point inhibitors is not evidenced or recommended for surgically resectable disease at diagnosis by nephrectomy.

- Adjuvant therapy with interferone-α cytokines following nephrectomy in non-metastatic RCC patients is not recommended as sorafenib, pazopanib, axitinib donot improve OS benefit after curative resection of primary tumor . Sunitinib is recommended by FDA [34].

Metastasis kidney cancer

Multidisciplinary environment of oncosurgeon, oncoradiologist, nursing care, dietary care and pharmacy support is needed for clear cell carcinoma, second-line therapy, non-clear cell histology, sarcomatoid variant RCC, cytoreductive nephrectomy, local oligometastasis, local therapy, radiation therapy, skeletal metastasis patients.

- Oligometastasis local therapy in stable conditions is option by giving very low radiation SBRT and/or resection. However, metastasectomy resection of metastasis locations (lung, thyroid and adrenal) may be needed after nephrectomy in surgically favorable early RCC patients. Same way, SBRT is recommended to treat RCC metastasis in locations of thoracic, abdominal, soft tissue, bone, brain.
- **Clear-cell carcinoma** untreated patients are recommended initial systemic treatment based on International metastatic RCC Database Consortium (IMDC) risk status. IMDC favorable-risk patients are recommended a combination of immunotherapy + VEGFR-TKI treatment. IMDC intermediate or poor risk
- **IMDC favorable risk** patients are recommended pembrolizumab+axitinib, lenvatinib+pembrolizumab, sunitinib, pazopanib, IMDC intermediate or poor risk patients are recommended combination immunotherapy+VEGFR-TKI therapy or combined therapy of ipilimumab+nivolumab, pembrolizumab+axitinib, nivolumab+cabozantinib, avelumab+axitinib, cabozantinib.
- **Second-line later therapy** to intolerant immune check-point inhibitor patients is given sunitinib,

pazopanib axitinib, cabozantinib, lenvatinib + everolimus treatment.

- **First-line** sunitinib/pazopanib intolerant patients are recommended VEGFR-TKI.
- **First-line** sunitinib/pazopanib tolerant progressing patients are recommended nivolumab/cabozantinib or lenvatinib + everolimus.

First-line VEGFR-TKI targeted therapy intolerant patients are recommended nivolumab, cabozantinib.

First-line VEGFR-TKI therapy tolerant progressing patients are recommended axitinib, lenvatinib + everolimus. Everolimus.

Progressing patients on or intolerant prior VEGFR-TKI and immune checkpoint inhibitor are recommended sunitinib, pazopanib, axitinib, cabozantinib, or lenvatinib + everolimus.

Non-clear cell RCC histology showing patients are managed by immunotherapy setting ipilimumab+nivolumab; pembrolizumab+axitinib; pembrolizumab monotherapy, cabozantinib, sunitinib.

Sarcomatoid poorly differentiated RCC patients are recommended by combined sunitinib + ipilimumab/nivolumab/axitinib/pembrolizumab/ cabozantinib immunotherapy to reduce sarcomatoid features [35].

Cytoreductive nephrectomy is recommended in de novo mRCC patients showing stable clinical response.

Local therapy in oligoprogression sites in RCC patients may be done by surgery, SBRT, cryotherapy, and/or radiofrequency RFA treatment. Stereotactic radiation therapy performs well to palliate the renal cancer symptoms.

Bone modifying agents zoledronic acid, denosumab inhibiting receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B (RANK) give relief in skeletal events.

Supportive care to patients.

ADRENAL CANCER

Nature of Adrenal Cancer

Adrenal cancer is a rare cancer also called adrenocortical cancer occurring at any stage right from infants and adults in age of 40s and 50s. Mostly adrenal gland growth is benign such as adenoma or pheochromocytoma. A most recent adrenal metastasis showed clinical outcomes within kidney cancer [36].

Symptoms: Most common symptoms of kidney cancer are blood in urine with complaints of lower back pain, abdomen lump, unexplained fatigue or tiredness, loss of appetite, rapid weight loss, swollen ankles and legs, high BP, low RBC count or anemia and hematuria.

Most common symptoms of adrenal cancer are muscle weakness, weight gain, pink or purple sketch marks on skin, irregular hormone changes in women (excessive facial hair, hair loss on head and irregular periods), in men (enlarged breast tissue and shrinking testicles), nausea, vomiting, abdominal bloating, back pain, fever, loss of appetite, weight loss.

Risks: Smoking, high BP, obesity, diet, genetic mutations such as Hippel-Lindau syndrome, leiomyomatosis, papillary renal cell carcinoma, polycystic disorders of kidneys, liver, pancreas, occupational exposure to heavy metals, cadmium, asbestos, petroleum products.

In adrenal gland cell, mutation DNA instructs cells to survive beyond healthy cells die to form accumulated cancer cells as tumors. These tumor cells break away and spread to other parts of the body in the form of metastasis. However, adrenal cancer happens mostly in people with inherited syndromes such as Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome, Carney complex, Li-Fraumeni syndrome, Lynch syndrome, Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN 1).

Diagnosis of Adrenal Cancer

1. High levels of adrenal hormones such as cortisol, aldosterone, androgens.

2. Presence of adrenal gland overgrowth locally and spread to other areas in the body such as lungs, liver by CT-PET, MRI.
3. Needle biopsy to identify cancer cells and type.

Optimal Treatment of Adrenal Gland Cancer:

Chemotherapy

Chemotherapy is used to kill adrenal cancer cells along with radiation therapy using high-powered X-ray and proton energy beams on growing adrenal glands in cancer. If chemotherapy and radiation therapy is insufficient, ablation therapy and surgery for removal of entire adrenal gland by adrenalectomy procedure are options alongwith removal of other parts of affected organs.

Post-surgery treatment for stopping recurrence of disease by chemosurgery or mitotane (Lysodren)

Next generation sequencing (NGS) improves the theranosis in renal cancer. Gene panels define well precision therapy plan by use of artificial neural networks, support vector machines, random forest artificial intelligence algorithms. These algorithms predict the performance of renal carcinoma specific theranostic genes by calculating receiver operating curveAUC [35].

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING IN RENAL AND ADRENAL CANCER THERANOSIS

What are Machine Learning Algorithms?

Machine learning AI algorithms are supervised or unsupervised learning methods.

- The supervised method extracts features from input data to predict, classify tumors and performing regression tasks. The classification is based on mapping input

data to discrete output level. The regression maps out an input to continuous output to predict survival.

- Unsupervised learning by k-means clustering and principal component analysis algorithms, learns from input inherent data structure (no levels) to do task of clustering.

1. Artificial neural networks (ANN) appear similar to brain neuron connections (intelligence) organized in cross layers with capabilities of doing different transfer functions or performing tasks of training sets. Dividing sets into training set, test set, validation sets. AI algorithms perform to train real datasets to achieve expected dataset after iterations, optimizing nodes and transfer function (network structure). However, ANN suffers from; 1. non-linear nature to minimize error function minimum between observed and expected outputs; 2. overfitting data by training data over-performance with low-performance of test data, to do least denoising.

2. Support Vector Machines (SVM) linear kernel learning process linear algorithms classify the renal tumors by looking a hyperplane separating two close-point between datasets or support vectors e.g. short and long survival. SVM algorithms reach absolute minimum of error function with least noise.

3. Random Forest RF algorithm combines predictions of many decision trees (forests) in to a single model. First, each decision tree learns from a subset of elements chosen randomly from available training data (bootstrap). Second, average of predictions of each decision tree (bagging) is calculated to obtain final predictions.

4. LASSO Regression is 'least-absolute-shrinkage-selection-operator' algorithm to perform independent variable selection (feature selection) and reduce variance for selecting predictor model.

5. Black Box Problem approach in the machine learning to large genomic data faces challenges of data-overfitting,

multiple non-linear operations, unknown influence of input variables on system behavior prediction or 'black-box' situation.

AI Predictors in ccRCC Cancer

Renal cancer molecular genes as input data of RNA-seq gene expression, methylation TCGA (The Cancer genome Atlas) data and transcript quantification, are used in prediction analysis of early stages I,II and late stages III, IV in following steps:

Recently reviewed machine learning algorithms were used in ccRCC diagnosis and prediction [46] using TCGA RNA-seq data:

1. Random forest based classifier, out of 20534 genes from TCGA source → 62 genes selected → RF classifier applied to x tumor samples → 89% sensitivity and 76.9% accuracy with auROC 0.778 to classify cancer and non-cancer samples based on recently cited metabolic pathways [37] as shown in Figure 2.

2. J48, naïve Bayes, sequential minimal optimization and random forest on RNA-seq data identify distinct expressed genes (DEG) between control and treated ccRCC condition by edgeR, DEseq2, R package for RCC stages I,II vs III and IV;

3. Calculation of differential methylation by R package LIMMA or MINFI package tool.

4. Initial data reduction or feature selection by clustering algorithm, principal component analysis or random forests, routine P-values and fold changes in RCC tumors.

5. Fast Correlation Based Feature algorithm and 'Symmetrical-Uncert-Attribute-Set-Eval' algorithm to perform discriminatory power (ROC) or to do SVM model for normal vs ccRCC.

6. Minimum Redundancy Maximum relevance algorithm to select features.

7. Fast Correlation Based Feature algorithm, SVM, MLP, Naïve Bayes methods to measure statistics, logistic

regression in ccRCC tumor stages I,II and III,IV.

8. Random Forest (varSelRF) algorithm to calculate adjusted false discovery rate to select variables for RCC tumor staging.

9. KNN, SVM, naïve Bayes, Random Forests, Shrunken centroids, LASSO regression algorithms to select features for papillary ccRCC tumor predictors and survival.

10. Supervised machine learning J48, naïve Bayes, sequential minimal optimization and random forest algorithms on RNA-seq TCGA data predicts stages I,II vs III, IV.

Several RCC specific genes CA9, FABP7, NDUFA4L2, PTHLH and SLC6A3 were also common and reported in a study using clustering/PCA algorithm. Using these selected variation filters and machine learning AI algorithms, unique linear or non-linear relationships can be established among gene datasets with diagnosis and success of treatment. For example, expression of 5-6 genes, expression magnitude, sociological, clinical and molecular inputs in large number of patients, as input in applied AI algorithm will learn the relationship to theragnosis and treatment response or prognosis. So, artificial intelligence perform deep learning or machine learning to classify tumors by integrating molecular information to select precise treatment as 'precision medicine'.

RNA-seq gene expression and methylation data from 'The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)' resource RSEM software showed most differentially expressed genes (DEGs) by trained-supervised edgeR, DEseqR limma, minifi package machine learning tools in control and RCC treated condition[38]. However, there was no potential correlation between groups of genes but may be gene-gene interactions. The second phase of the analyses consists in a huge initial data reduction in feature

selection or discriminating trained data using clustering algorithms, principal component analysis or random forests along with statistical P-values, fold changes [39]. Other feature selection and analysis methods are also in use such as 'Symmetrical-Uncert-Attribute-Set-Eval' and 'Fast Correlation Based Feature' algorithms based on performance of discriminatory power (ROC) or on performance of SVM model, minimum redundancy maximum relevance MRMR methods and 'Fast Correlation Based Feature' algorithm or joint statistical measures and logistic regression [40]. Thus, integration of multimodal RNA-seq data with feature selection is state-of-art for prediction of kidney cancer survival. Different prediction algorithms applied on different RCC subtypes show concerns with different gene types and numbers. Algorithms employing SVM predict better the patient survival, and algorithms distinguish early and late tumor stages well.

CLINICAL TRIALS ON RENAL CANCER WITH ADRENAL METASTASES

Adrenal mass in RCC is rare disease and few clinical studies are reported. A classical clinical study on twelve adrenal metastatic patients reported long-time 0-250 months for RCC diagnosis to adrenal metastasis development with malignancy +ve histology (11/12) and translocation-type histology (1/12) alongwith imaging scan. Four patients showed initial metastasis disease to adrenal metastasis within 0-111 months (4/12). Twelve patients were included in this retrospective report [34]. Eleven had clear cell histology, but one had translocation-type histology. Patient characteristics are summarized in Table 4. The median time from RCC diagnosis to adrenal metastasis was 68 months (range 0-252 months), and the median time from initial metastatic

disease to appearance of adrenal metastasis was 15 months (range 0–111 months). A typical CT-PET scan showing adrenal metastases is depicted in Figure 4. The

sites of metastases are summarized in Figure 4. Four patients had bilateral adrenal metastases [2].

Table 4:-Patient summaries of advanced renal cancer with adrenal metastases [2].

Patient characteristic	No. (%)
Median age (range)	49.5 years; range 41–80 years
Gender: male/female	12 (100%)/0 (0%)
Race: African/Caucasian/Hispanic	1 (8.3%)/10 (83.4%)/1 (8.3%)
Unilateral/bilateral	9 (75%)/3 (25%)
Nephrectomy	11 (91.7%)/1 (8.3%)
Histology: clear cell/translocation xp11	11 (91.7%)/1 (8.3%)
Fuhrman Grade: 2/3/unknown	5 (42%)/4 (33%)/3 (25%)
Median time to adrenal mets (range)	68 months (0–252 months)
Systemic therapy: IL-2/ICI/none/VEGF	3 (25%)/5 (41%)/3 (25%)/1 (9%)
Systemic therapy: anti-VEGF therapy	6 (50%)
Local therapy: Surgery/cryotherapy/microwave/none	3 (25%)/6 (50%)/1 (8%)/2 (17%)
IMDC risk: Fav/Int/poor	4 (33.3%)/8 (66.7%)/0 (0%)

Fig.4:-Computed tomography and positron emission tomography imaging showing adrenal gland metastasis. Reproduced with permission from reference [2].

The proliferative behavior of metastasis is commonly observed at distant organs as site of lungs, bones, left and right adrenal glands, soft tissues, lymph nodes and

pancreas [41]. The distribution of adrenal gland cancer metastasis in different organs is shown in Figure 5.

Fig.5:-Distribution of location of distant metastases in nine patients with multiple sites of proliferated metastases. Reproduced with permission from reference [2].

In other clinical trial [42], next-generation sequencing and programmed cell death ligand 1(PD-L1-ve) IHC-negative tests are illustrated in the following Table 3. All RCC patients had pathogenic PBRM1 (3/5), SETD2(2/5) and VHL(4/5) mutations and no BAP1 mutation. Tumor mutation

burden was <5 mutation/megabase in all patients. These patients had no BRCA1 or BRCA2 mutations or any DNA repair mutations. Two patients showed NGS in both primary tumor and adrenal or mediastinal metastasis biopsies.

Table 5:-Clinical course and molecular profile of renal cancer cases. Illustrated from reference [2]

Case number/ Location	NGS/IHC results	Clinical course
Case 1 Adrenal	<i>PBRM1</i> exon 21 <i>KDM5C</i> Exon 4 TUBB3 40% ERCC10%	Received IL-2 for RCC with bone mets with CR Relapsed with bilateral adrenal metastases, 11 and 12.5 years after IL-2 therapy. Treated with local therapy, cryo therapy on one lesion and surgery on the other.
Case 2 KidneyAdrenal	<i>PBRM1</i> exon 18 <i>SETD2</i> exon 10 <i>VHL</i> exon 1 <i>PBRM1</i> exon 18 <i>SETD2</i> exon 10 <i>VHL</i> exon 1	Clear cell RCC post-nephrectomy Relapsed with adrenal metastasis, treated with local therapy. No systemic therapy.
Case 4 Kidney Mediastinal	<i>VHL</i> exon 1 <i>CDKN1B</i> exon 1 <i>VHL</i> exon 1 <i>CDKN2A</i> exon 2	Clear cell RCC post-nephrectomy Relapsed with lung metastases 46 months after and treated with ICI. Response seen in lung, but adrenal metastases appeared 67 months after nephrectomy as sites of PD during ICI therapy. Responding well

Case number/ Location	NGS/IHC results	Clinical course
		currently to TKI therapy.
Case 6 Kidney	<i>SETD2</i> exon 3 <i>ATM</i> VUS exon 26 <i>VHL</i> exon 2	Synchronous presentation with kidney mass and metastases to lung and bone. Received ICI therapy and had response at other sites but PD with new adrenal metastases. Responding well currently to TKI therapy.
Case 7 Adrenal Lung	<i>PBRM1</i> exon 26 <i>SETD2</i> exon 16 <i>VHL</i> exon 2 ERCC 100% IHC	Post-nephrectomy presented with lung metastases. Received IL-2 and progressed. Treated with ICI and had a response in lung but adrenal metastasis emerged. Treated with local therapy.

NGS, next-generation sequencing; IHC, immunohistochemistry; PD-L1, programmed death ligand-1; Int, intermediate; VUS, variant of uncertain significance; IL-2, interleukin-2; ICI, immune checkpoint inhibitor; RCC, renal cell carcinoma.

OPTIMAL MANAGEMENT OF RCC WITH ADRENAL METASTASIS

A clinical study on optimal management of twelve RCC patients with adrenal mass [2] showed distinct chemotherapy response:

- Three patients (3/12) presented adrenal metastases only, and showed complete remission with local therapy treatment of high-dose IL-2. One patient (1/12) received high-dose IL-2 for relapsed solitary adrenal metastasis 11 years after initial cryotherapy treatment. This patient developed metastasis in other side adrenal 18 months later and that was treated with surgical resection. The patient showed

complete remission after surgical resection.

- Other two patients received IL-2 therapy, one patient had unresectable large adrenal masses and showed response to antivasular therapy while other patient improved on IL-2 therapy with a response to ipilimumab and nivolumab treatment at all sites except in the adrenal gland. Later, adrenal lesion was treated with cryoablation.
- Five patients (5/12) were treated with immune checkpoint inhibitor (ICI) and one patient(1/12) patient received antivasular therapy. Out of five ICI-based regimens on ipilimumab + nivolumab, two patients (2/5) treated with axitinib + pembrolizumab, avelumab + adenosine receptor inhibitor in one patient and bevacizumab or atezolizumab in other patient. ICI therapy was followed by ablation of residual adrenal metastases in three patients. The systemic and local therapy management is summarized in Figure 6.

Fig.6:-Management flow chart shows adrenal metastases in twelve renal cancer patients. Overlap is seen as some patients received multiple different types of therapies.

Local therapy and Management of Adrenal Gland Metastases:

Adrenal gland metastases fall into three main categories:

1. De novo adrenal metastases only
2. Residual/sanctuary adrenal metastases (only sites of disease resistant to immunotherapy)
3. Adrenal metastases as component of RCC progression

The ICI based regimens in RCC, improved the clinical outcomes and high response rates over other tyrosine kinase inhibitors such as pazopanib or cabozantinib. In the case of ICI thresistance, local therapy is needed.

Adrenal gland metastases demonstrate the resistance to immune check-point inhibitor (ICI) based therapy.

1. Surgical resection is done by cryoblation/microwave ablation or stereotactic radiation therapy.
2. Systemic VEGF-TKI therapy is used to reduce tumor size and then local immune therapy to do complete remission.
3. Combined stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT) and immune check-point-based systemic therapy demonstrate good response rates [43]. For malignant residual solitary adrenal melanoma lesions in sanctuary site after immune check-point based

systemic pembrolizumab therapy, local therapy of metastases with surgery resection, percutaneous cryoablation/microwave ablation and SBRT is choice [44][45].

Authors believe that molecular profiling based on NGS biomarkers may also predict personalized therapeutic decisions in adrenal malignancies. Several indicators such as absent BAP1 mutation, absent PD-L1 expression, low TMB mutation, absent PBRM1 mutation, low VHL mutations predict higher likelihood of better prognosis, good response to ICI and VEGF therapies. Moreover, proteomics, epigenomics, metabolomics predictors may be other proven predictors in adrenal malignancies.

Adrenal gland lesions stay as sanctuary sites. Glucocorticoids in adrenal cortex facilitate immune-resistant metastasis growth when immunosuppressive milieu prevents entry of lymphocytes. Inflammatory biomarkers and lymphocytes indicate the immune check-point inhibition and altered immune-resistant pathways.

EMERGING VIRTUAL REALITY MODELS IN ROBOTIC RENAL PARTIAL NEPHRECTOMY

Three-dimensional virtual reality models from CT-MRI imaging of patients undergoing robotic assisted partial

nephrectomy have high impact on pre-surgical planning as shown in Figure 4. However, major challenge is 3D view reconstruction obtained from 2D imaging. Author acquired experimental mice renal 3D 21T MRI images usable to reconstruct 3D VR models [6]. Now state-of-art is available for clinical 3D VR models for viewing them on surgeon's smart phone and on self VR headset [46]. Still it is in infancy.

PRESENT STATE-OF-ART AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In present time, personalized renal cancer therapy plan based on precise patient's clinical and molecular (biochemical-genetic) variables is state-of-art. For RCC molecular predictive biomarkers, next-generation sequencing methods serve to identify discriminative molecular features and variables. These molecular variables such as transcripts, proteins and metabolites are used as data inputs as RCC therapeutic targets in AI algorithms to derive non-linear / linear relationships among previous datasets and reproduce (machine learning) better, faster and robust with minimum noise output tumor prediction (classification, disease behavior and treatment response). However, machine learning process uses internal model of reality-functioning in unknown 'black box' manner. These machine learning methods easily identify, stratify patients at high risk expression profile but low-stage treatable tumors by adjuvant therapy with care and attention. Same way, patients at low risk expression profile but high-grade tumor stage can be identified as treatable with less aggressive chemotherapy under close observation. All these above approaches suffer from a challenge of molecular heterogeneity of kidney tumors.

Different algorithms choose groups of different genes with similar expression profiles (molecular features) as one class.

As a result, survival predictors derived from AI based and non-AI based cannot be compared because of different variable selection means less number in AI based algorithm as optimized 'class' that derives indistinguishable normograms when C-index is provided but AUC distinguished well normograms for 3-year (AUC 0.813) and 5-year (AUC 0.799) survival by integrating expression data of high ISUP (International Society of Urological Pathology) grade of ccRCC [47].

The gene expression data was integrated with gene mutation data to increase the accuracy of predictions in prognosis [48]. It is difficult to train an expert system to measure magnitude of specific mutation burden (genetic disease) as different mutation effects of one gene depend on many gene functions and mutation locations on the gene. It requires further all mutations grouping together that diminishes the predictive power of expert systems. However, TCGA data will be great source of deriving gender-, ethnic- and RCC variant-specific predictors of renal cancer in near future.

The increase in RCC prevalence and failure of conventional therapy to reduce mortality rates in RCC patients further indicate that need of alternate strategies for cancer management. The nanotechnology seems option in early tumor diagnosis and chemoprevention for cancer therapy.

CONCLUSION

Renal cancer with adrenal metastases present a distinct pattern of relapse or residual local site in advanced RCC. The relapse or residual disease in adrenals may be detected after durable remission at other sites. Immunosuppressive tumor environment milieu in adrenal cortex is source of metastasis and drug resistance or chemotherapy failure. Presently, treatment is quite expensive, less effective with adverse effects. Next-generation sequencing, mutations, molecular profiling

seem good early RCC predictors. Chemoprevention, combined chemotherapy with immunotherapy, Anti-VEGRF-TKI therapy remains choice of good therapeutic response. Artificial intelligence predictors serve as trained bioinformatic prognostic markers derived from new biochemical, metabolic and genetic variation datasets in renal carcinoma. Machine learning methods perform well but it is still far from use of artificial intelligence to achieve real clinical use.

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